

Soil biological indicators for monitoring soil health

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- Soil functioning is at risk due to biodiversity loss
- Sufficient know-how is available to monitor soil biodiversity and soil health
- Soil health, including soil biodiversity, should be assessed using a tiered approach
- Suitable biological indicators have been identified for Tier I application across EU

INTRODUCTION

The EU Soil Mission defined “Soil Health” as *“the continued capacity of soils to support ecosystem services”*. Soil biodiversity supports most of those services, but degradation processes are compromising this capacity. Although many biological indicators for assessing soil health have been proposed, there is limited international consensus on the most effective ones or on how to optimize monitoring schemes for policy relevance and scientific robustness. However, in the last two decades, several national and EU projects have evaluated the suitability of indicators for monitoring schemes. We conclude that sufficient methodology and know-how are now available to start the EU-wide implementation of a minimum set of biological indicators to monitor soil biodiversity and soil health.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Most of the documented and projected changes in biodiversity are based on observations of non-soil organisms. However, it is important to emphasize that almost 60% of all species on Earth are found in soil (Anthony et al., 2023). This biodiversity is increasingly at risk due to soil threats, highlighting the urgent need for monitoring its status and trends across the EU. While it is desirable to reduce the logistical and cost implications of incorporating biological indicators into national monitoring programs, the complexity of soil biota, their interactions, and the varying scales at which they function make it impossible to fully capture them with a single indicator. Though the definition of a

“minimum set” of indicators for the assessment of soil health is desirable, a more flexible and adaptable approach may be better suited to addressing the soil functions and ecosystem services relevant in distinct environmental and management contexts. This policy brief presents the MINOTAUR consortium’s perspective on the most suitable bioindicators for soil health assessment. The recommendations aim to better integrate scientific findings on soil health indicators into EU policies to enhance ecosystem sustainability and resilience (Di Gregorio et al., 2025), and aid the ongoing preparation of Member States (MS) for national monitoring of soil health and biodiversity by 2030, under the new Soil Monitoring Law (EC, 2023).

CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF METHODS

In the last two decades, several sets of biological indicators have been proposed for monitoring at the EU scale. A list of criteria was defined based on a “logical sieve” approach (Stone et al., 2016), which provided a ranking of appropriate indicators to be adopted according to specific context scenarios. Most of these are also recommended by the European Environmental Agency (EEA-report, 2023). However, recent inventories of existing soil monitoring networks showed that only few biological indicators are implemented by MS (Faber et al., 2022), with soil respiration, microbial biomass and earthworm communities being most commonly used. However, soil respiration by itself only measures overall biological activity and does not provide information about the types of organisms in the soil, their diversity, or their functions. Earthworms are useful indicators of

soil functions but account for only a small share of the species living in soil, offering limited insight into overall biodiversity. No single indicator tells the complete story. Thus, in MINOTAUR, we combined indicators that capture the composition of soil communities and their diversity (structural/taxonomic diversity), as well as their functions (“functional diversity”), considering the notion that most soil organisms may be classified in three main functional groups according to their dominant contribution to soil processes and ecosystem services (El Mujtar et al., 2019):

- 1) **Chemical engineers** (Microbes), which decompose and mineralize organic matter, transform residues into nutrients, and play a key role in bioremediation and plant symbiosis;
- 2) **Biological regulators** (Micro- and Mesofauna), which control the activity of chemical engineers, forming a crucial link in the food web by grazing, comminution, predation or parasitism, controlling soil-borne pests and diseases;
- 3) **Ecosystem engineers** (Macrofauna), which restructure the soil matrix, create microhabitats, and dispersing other soil organisms. Their bioturbation activities promote water regulation, root growth and soil fertility.

Notably, this classification represents a simplification, as species from different functional groups can contribute to multiple soil processes. Also, the abundance of each functional group individually or the overall taxonomic diversity does not always directly relate to the soil health status (e.g., high abundance of pathogens). Thus, we argue that to provide comprehensive and reliable information about soil health status it is needed to overall assess both the composition of biological groups, as well as soil functions that they can mediate. Thus, **taxonomical and functional diversity should be considered simultaneously** for monitoring purposes, as both aspects sustain soil ecosystem functioning and services, including food security and one health. Hence, we suggest that a subset of both functional and structural indicators (ideally representing all three functional groups of organisms) from the

proposed **Tier I list (table 1)**, should be selected.

A TIERED APPROACH

Based on the above-mentioned principles and criteria, a stepwise approach is proposed here, in alignment with recommendations of the ENVASSO, EcoFINDERS, and EJP Soil-SIREN projects. This approach includes an initial set of structural and functional indicators to be standardized across the EU, which are strongly recommended as mandatory descriptors for all MS for an initial assessment of soil health status. Given the intricate relationships between soil biodiversity, soil functioning and the resulting provision of ecosystem services, monitoring soil health necessitates the use of multiple biological indicators that offer complementary insights. While this complexity may render monitoring at national scale laborious and costly, **tiering of the monitoring process would increase cost-efficiency substantially**. For example, a first tier can be set up as a screening step that can trigger additional - more site-specific - investigation when potential concerns are identified. Such an approach is already implemented in environmental risk assessment of contaminated soils. In a tiered approach, ideally, one or two biological indicators can be applied for a first general screening. But here is the catch: at present no single biological indicator has well-established target or threshold values to effectively screen for soil health, not even under the most common contexts of soil type and land use. Therefore, while we advocate for a tiered approach, we **recommend the application of a larger number of biological indicators in Tier I**, at least in an initial period, to build a reference database (“baseline”) for developing screening criteria in the near future.

For the selection of appropriate biological indicators for Tier I monitoring at national scale, we observe different needs and priorities between MS. From a scientific viewpoint, a full harmonization of indicators across the EU is advisable for reasons of comparability. However, maintaining non-harmonized indicators may also be valid,

particularly where continuation of existing long-term monitoring (chronosequences) is concerned. **A Tier II group may then be adopted when Tier I results indicate 'not healthy' conditions**, or when local authorities require additional information to identify specific soil threats.

A Tier II group was not defined in MINOTAUR but it may include additional (and even non-harmonized) descriptors that can be voluntarily selected by MS on a case-by-case basis, e.g., depending on soil type, climate,

land use and management, according to the above-mentioned “logical sieve” approach. All the recommended indicators have been scientifically validated, are cost-effective, supported by standard methods and have been successfully implemented in important monitoring initiatives ongoing at national and international scales (i.e., JRC-LUCAS and SOILBON programmes). Even for those not standardized yet (i.e., DNA metabarcoding), well established procedures are available and could be easily standardized.

Table 1 - Tier I group of recommended indicators, a brief description and available standard or reference methods. Cost estimations are based on Bispo et al. 2024.

Priority level	Recommended indicators	Brief description	Methodology	Cost	
Tier I	Functional Indicators	Microbial biomass C	Amount of microbial biomass per gram soil	ISO 14 240-1 / -2 EN ISO 11 063	20-30€/sample
		Microbial respiration	Production of CO ₂ per amount of soil	ISO 16072:2002	20-30€/sample
		Enzyme activity	Measurement of several hydrolase activities in soil	ISO 14 238 ISO/TS 22 939 ISO 23 753-1 ISO 23 753-2	20-80€ for each enzyme
	Structural indicators	Ecosystem engineers (Macrofauna)	Structural and functional diversity (earthworms)	ISO 23611-1:2018 and Fusaro et al., 2018	30-140€
		Biological regulators (Mesofauna)	Structural and functional diversity	QBS-ar (Parisi et al., 2005)	75-140€
		Biological regulators (Microfauna)	Structural and functional diversity (nematodes)	Bongers and Ferris 1999	30-140€
		Chemical engineers (Microorganisms)	Structural diversity of soil microbiota (bacteria, archaea, fungi)	DNA metabarcoding (ISO 11063:2020) and Plassart et al., 2012	75-100€ for each target group

SENSITIVITY AND THRESHOLDS

To test their sensitivity to soil disturbances under field conditions, the Tier I group of indicators was **simultaneously** tested in 9 long-term experimental sites (LTEs) across different ranges of soil type, climate, and management practices - collectively referred to as “context scenarios”. These selected LTEs have been running by MINOTAUR partner institutions for more than a decade and encompass a large gradient of pedoclimatic conditions and are located across eight EU countries. All experiments assessed the effects of minimizing soil disturbance by comparing different management intensity (standard tillage vs. reduced or no-tillage) and/or implementing distinct fertilization approaches (mineral vs. organic amendments). Briefly, the results showed that: i) All the indicators’ values were

significantly affected by the LTE pedoclimatic conditions; ii) All the recommended indicators were significantly sensitive to different managements and/or fertilization practices of the LTEs; iii) The sensitivity of the recommended indicators varied with the type of disturbance (i.e., tillage or fertilization); iv) Different indicators (and their metrics) may have contrasting trends under the same condition (i.e., microbial diversity and micro/macro fauna diversity under different tillage intensity), confirming that the use of a single bioindicator may lead to a wrong or misleading conclusion (Aponete et al., 2024). Thus, **we strongly recommend the adoption of all the Tier-1 set of indicators, to understand the status/health of soil**. Moreover, the definition of a ‘**threshold**’ value, above or below which a soil could be defined as “not

healthy”, is recommended only when adequate data are available in the context of soil type and land use. In fact, in lack of sufficient reference data MS can just monitor changes and trends (Matson et al., 2024). In conclusion, we welcome the EU proposal for a new Directive for Soil Monitoring and Resilience (COM(2023) 416), as crucial means to legally protect soils as an essential part of

the ecosystem and to accomplish EU Green Deal objectives. However, in the implementation of the SML we recommend that MS invest in biological indicators to build a robust reference database for both structural and functional indicators. This will facilitate the development of evaluation criteria in a nationally relevant context of soil type and land use.

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY MAKERS

Recommendation One: A tiered approach.

A “tiered system” of biological indicators is proposed: (1) Tier I group, including a first set of indicators harmonized for all cases; (2) Tier II group (to be defined by each MS), including many other additional available indicators that may be selected case by case and applied when Tier I group’s results return “not healthy”, depending on the specific aims and conditions of the monitoring program.

Recommendation Two: Apply all indicators of Tier I group.

Indicators of the Tier I group are standardized, scientifically robust and cost-effective. Although from the scientific point of view all are applied together, monitoring programs should adopt at least both structural and functional indicators when not adopting all.

Recommendation Three: A holistic integration of multiple soil health indicators (biological, chemical, physical) is highly recommended.

Soil health should be monitored not only with chemical-physical analyses, but also with biological indicators directly related to soil biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services. Moreover, indicators should be evaluated in the context of the local environment (soil texture, climate, land use and management).

Recommendation Four: Monitoring changes rather than applying thresholds.

Given the current scarcity of background data, we recommend for the short-term to monitor mere trends; target or threshold values may be developed when ample data are available.

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